

Evaluation of Bacterial Load in Broiler Meat in Slaughterhouses in Khartoum State

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Abstract

A total of 70 swab samples were collected from two types of broiler slaughterhouses (automatic and manual), in Jabelawlia locality in Khartoum State. The objective of this study was to evaluate the bacterial count in broiler carcasses at three process steps during broiler processing. These were: after slaughtering, after scalding, and after chilling. The samples were collected from three sites in broiler carcasses namely: leg, neck, and brisket; in addition to workers' hands. All swab samples were transported in peptone water and examined in the laboratory for total Viable Count (TVC). The study revealed that the highest TVC in the automatic slaughterhouse was found in the worker's hands during scalding process step (12.0 ± 10.9 cfu/cm²) and the lowest was in the brisket and worker's hands during the chilling process step (0.3 ± 1.7 cfu/cm²). The highest bacterial load in the manual slaughterhouse was found after the scalding process step in the legs (20.5 ± 14.3 cfu/cm²), and the lowest was found in the neck after chilling process step (5.0 ± 7.07). Means and standard deviation (SD) of TVC of in different process steps in the investigated slaughterhouses showed no significant differences. It could be concluded that TVC was high in manual slaughtering than in automatic slaughtering systems.

Keywords: Total Viable Count; Broiler contamination; Process steps; Slaughterhouse.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between authors. Author (1) collected the research data, conducted laboratory analysis, and contribute to drafting the initial manuscript. Author (2) conceptualized the initial idea, performed supervision over the research, and drafted the initial manuscript. Author (3) edited, reviewed the final manuscript, and carried out correspondence duties. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

INTRODUCTION

Meat is considered as an important source of proteins to man and is the most perishable of all important foods because of its rich nutrients that supports microbial growth (Ukut *et al.*, 2010).

Epidemiological data suggested that contaminated products of animal origin especially poultry contribute significantly to food borne diseases.

Each year, millions of people worldwide suffer from food-borne diseases (WHO, 2000), and illness resulting from the consumption of contaminated foods has become one of the most widespread public health problems in contemporary society (Notermans *et al.*, 1995).

Reduction of raw poultry contamination levels have a large impact on reducing the incidence of illness (Keener *et al.*, 2004).

WHO (2000) mentioned that the studies conducted by research institutions in Sudan on microbial contamination in meat processing plants revealed high levels of microbiological contamination due to the absence of implementation of GMPS and GHPS.

Moreover, contamination of meat can result from contaminated working surfaces, equipment and workers' hands used in the processing. Mustafa et al. (2016) reported that several factors contribute to meat contamination in Khartoum State, which are obviously seen from the poor handling during processing.

Several research studies evaluated microbial contamination of broiler carcasses in Khartoum State and recommended the implementation of the prerequisites programs of the HACCP system in poultry meat industry, as it involves the constant monitoring of all steps of the process (Youssif Ayman, 2015; Abdalla, et al., 2013). Other researchers recommended the direct implementation of the HACCP system (Ahmed, 2014; MOHAMED-NOOR et al., 2012).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study area and design**

An analytical study was carried out during the year 2018 in Jabelawlia locality in Khartoum State.

- **Data collection**

Microbiological tests were used to evaluate TVC from two types of poultry slaughterhouses namely: automatic and manual

- **Sample size and sampling technique**

A total of 70 sterile cotton swab samples were collected by skin scraping (outside layer) from leg, neck, brisket after three process steps: defeathering scalding, and chilling (table 1).

Any process steps of defeathering had different workers. Additionally, swab samples were collected from workers' hands after scalding and chilling process steps. Swabs were rubbed over an area of 1cm² and were placed in 2 ml sterile normal saline and transported in ice box (4 °C) to the Central Veterinary Research Laboratory for microbiological analysis.

- **Microbial analysis**

Total Viable Count was performed using the method of Miles and Misra (1938).

- **Statistical analysis**

The collected data were coded and analyzed using Statistical Packaging for the Social Sciences (SPSS/PCversion21 for windows). Data were analyzed for Descriptive Statistical Analysis.

Table 1: Swabs samples from different sites and process steps in the investigated slaughterhouses

Sample site	Automatic slaughterhouse (No.)	Manual slaughterhouse (No.)	Total
Leg:			
After Defeathering	5	5	10
After Scalding	4	4	8
After Chilling	4	4	8
Neck:			
After Scalding	4	4	8
After Chilling	4	4	8
Brisket:			
After Scalding	4	4	8
After Chilling	4	4	8
Workers' hands:			
After Scalding	3	3	6
After Chilling	3	3	6
Total	35	35	70

RESULTS

- **Bacterial load in automatic slaughterhouse**

The highest bacterial TVC in automatic slaughterhouse was found in the workers' hands during scalding process step (12.0 ±10.9 cfu/cm²) and the lowest was in the brisket and workers' hands during chilling process step (0.3 ± 1.7 cfu/cm²) (table 2).

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of TVC in different process steps in the automatic slaughterhouse

Site Stage	Leg (n= 13)	Neck (n=8)	Brisket (n= 8)	Workers' hands (n =6)
After defeathering	2.6 ±5.9	not done	not done	not done
After scalding	9.9 ± 9.9	0.4 ± 2	5.7 ± 7.5	12.0 ±10.9
After chilling	6.0 ±7.7	5.7 ±7.5	0.3 ± 1.7	0.3 ±1.7

- **Bacterial load in manual slaughterhouse:**

The highest bacterial load in the manual slaughterhouse was found after the scalding process step in the legs (20.5 ± 14.3 cfu/cm²), and the lowest was found after chilling process step in the neck (5.0 ± 7.07). Workers' hands recorded 11.2 ± 10.5 cfu/cm² after scalding process step and 12.5 ± 11.1 cfu/cm² after chilling process step.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation (SD) of TVC counts in different sites and process steps of broiler carcasses in the manual slaughterhouse

Site Stage	Leg (n= 13)	Neck (n= 8)	Brisket (n= 8)	Workers' hand (n= 6)
After defeathering	17.1 ± 13.07	not done	not done	not done
After scalding	20.5 ± 14.3	18.1 ± 13.4	17.0 ± 13.03	11.2 ± 10.5
After chilling	10.5 ± 10.2	5.0 ± 7.07	8.9 ± 9.43	12.5 ± 11.1

As shown in table (4) the manual slaughterhouse means and standard deviation at different process steps was 17.1 ± 13 cfu/cm² after slaughtering, 18.5 ± 13.6 cfu/cm² after scalding, and 8.1 ± 9.0 cfu/cm² chilling process steps. Workers' hands recorded 11.8 ± 10.8 cfu/cm².

Automatic slaughterhouse means and standard deviation revealed 2.6 ± 5.0 , after slaughtering process step, 5.3 ± 7.2 after scalding and 4.0 ± 6.3 after chilling process step. Workers' hands recorded 0.6 ± 2.4 cfu/cm².

Table 4: Means and standard deviation (SD) of TVC of in different process steps in the investigated slaughterhouses

Process step	Mean (log ₁₀ cfu /cm ²) & Standard deviation		Sig. Significant difference
	Automatic slaughterhouse	Manual slaughterhouse	
After defeathering	2.6 ± 5.0	17.1 ± 13	*N.S.
After scalding	5.3 ± 7.2	18.5 ± 13.6	*N.S.
After chilling	4.0 ± 6.3	8.1 ± 9.0	*N.S.
Worker's hands	0.6 ± 2.4	11.8 ± 10.8	*N.S.

*Not Significant

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study was to evaluate the bacterial count in broiler carcasses at three process steps during broiler processing in automatic and manual slaughterhouses.

This study revealed small variation in contamination of workers hands after scalding process step (dirty zone) in both the automatic and manual slaughterhouses (12.0 ± 10.9 Vs 11.2 ± 10.5), respectively. While higher variation in contamination of workers hands was recorded after chilling process step (clean zone) in both the automatic and manual slaughterhouses (0.3 ± 1.7 Vs 12.5 ± 11.1), respectively.

The higher contamination of workers hands specially in the automatic slaughterhouse may be due to lack of monitoring of hygienic practices of workers.

Lower results for average aerobic count of workers hands in the dirty zone were reported by Mohammed (2000) who found 8.54×10^5 CFU/10cm² and 1.36×10^5 CFU/10cm² in dirty and clean zone, respectively.

Very lower results for average aerobic count of workers hands were also reported by GABEER et al 2012 who found 1.3 ± 0.02 and 1.4 ± 0.01 log₁₀ CFU cm² at legs and breast sites, respectively.

This study revealed higher variation in bacterial count in the leg site after defeathering in both automatic and manual slaughterhouses (2.6 ± 5.9 Vs. 17.1 ± 13.07).

Higher TVCs were recorded by MOHAMED-NOOR et al. (2012) who found $9.99 \pm 0.01 \log_{10}$ CFU/cm² in the back process step in automatic slaughterhouse in Khartoum State

The current study revealed higher TVCs contamination in brisket site after scalding process step in manual slaughterhouse (17.0 ± 13.03), while lower counts were recorded in automatic slaughterhouse (5.7 ± 7.5). The lower count in the automatic slaughterhouse may be attributed to the fact that appropriate scalding water temperature was used.

Higher findings ($9.96 \pm 0.01 \log_{10}$ CFU/cm²) for contamination of the leg site after scalding process steps were reported by MOHAMED-NOOR et al. (2012) in automatic slaughterhouse in Khartoum State.

In this research higher TVC count were found in the leg and brisket sites (10.5 ± 10.2 Vs. 8.9 ± 9.43), respectively after chilling process steps in manual slaughterhouse. While very low count (0.3 ± 1.7) was recorded in brisket site in automatic slaughterhouse. This study revealed that the TVC in the automatic slaughterhouse was influenced by the chilling process step.

This finding agrees with Irena *et al.* (2011), in Czech slaughterhouse who found that the total viable count (TVC) of poultry carcasses decreased during processing to 4.6 log cfu/cm².

Higher counts in manual slaughterhouse may be attributed to lack of personal hygiene, dirty workers' hands, and contaminated equipment.

Slightly higher results were reported by GABEER et al (2012) and MOHAMED-NOOR et al. (2012) in automatic slaughterhouses in Khartoum State who recorded $1.8 \pm 0.70 \log_{10}$ CFU cm² and $1.86 \pm 0.01 \log_{10}$ CFU/cm², respectively for contamination of brisket site after chilling process step.

Higher bacterial contamination in poultry meat carcasses in manual slaughterhouses may affect the quality of poultry meat (Omer and Abdelrahman, 2015).

Ways used to reduce higher bacterial counts in poultry processing plants are to apply a proper Food Safety Management System (Good Hygienic Practices (GHPs) and Good Manufacturing Practices (GMPs) (Akinnibosun and Imade, 2015; Howlett et al., 2010).

CONCLUSION

It could be concluded that higher bacterial contamination in poultry meat carcasses were found in manual slaughterhouse which may affect the quality of poultry meat and jeopardize consumers' health.

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Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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